

Deliverable 5.3

Report on the pilot activities including impact assessment

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Executive Summary

The SEADE project set out to strengthen collaboration between Europe and Sub-Saharan Africa by piloting a portfolio of services on the ENRICH in Africa platform designed to bridge the gap between research outcomes and market opportunities. These services were tested in Ghana, Kenya, Senegal, and South Africa through a structured approach: pilot-lead training, in-person workshops, ongoing support, and feedback sessions. A human-centred methodology guided the work, ensuring that the experiences of innovators, hubs, and researchers shaped the findings.

The pilots confirmed strong interest and engagement across all regions. In Ghana, participants highlighted the importance of clear onboarding materials and visibility of local hubs within the digital ecosystem. Senegalese stakeholders valued the new tools and services but called for French translation, simplified registration, and better geographical balance in opportunities. In Kenya, IoT innovators connected their pressing needs—such as regulatory barriers, limited prototyping resources, and access to finance—with the solutions provided by EiA services, demonstrating the platform’s practical relevance. In South Africa, feedback showed 100% adoption intent and high usability ratings, while also pointing to areas for refinement, particularly the usability of the STR Actor dashboard and stronger contextual alignment with the national ecosystem.

Taken together, these results provide strong evidence that the SEADE services are both relevant and in demand. They also reveal clear priorities for improvement: language inclusivity, streamlined onboarding, enriched content and repositories, and localisation of services to regional contexts. The pilots demonstrate that a human-centred, feedback-driven approach can accelerate adoption and ensure that tools are genuinely useful to end users. The findings now offer a concrete basis for refining the EiAC digital platform including the SEADE digital environment and associated services to better serve innovators and research actors across Africa and Europe.

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Abbreviations

AAU	Association of African Universities
ASSEK	Association of Startup and SME Enablers of Kenya
BIC Africa	Business and Innovation Centre Africa
BOND	Bondy Innovation
BPI	Bpifrance
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
EiA	ENRICH in Africa
EiAC	ENRICH in Africa Center
EU	European Union
GIZ	Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit
HAPA	Hapa Foundation
IoT	Internet of Things
KCIH	Kumasi City Incubation Hub
MESTI	Ministry of Environment, Science, Technology and Innovation (Ghana)
TIA	Technology Innovation Agency
WAZI	Waziup e.V.

1. Introduction

Across Africa and Europe, researchers and innovators often face fragmented ecosystems that limit their ability to transform ideas into sustainable market solutions. The SEADE project was conceived to address this challenge by strengthening cooperation between the two continents and building a seamless route-to-market pathway for research and innovation actors. At the heart of this vision lies the piloting of a portfolio of tools and services designed to enhance collaboration, expand access to funding and capacity-building, and open new opportunities for innovators to scale their work.

Task 5.3 focused on testing these tools and services on the EiAC platform in four pilot regions: Ghana, Kenya, Senegal, and South Africa. The objective was not only to confirm their technical functionality but also to assess their relevance and usability within diverse innovation ecosystems. Each pilot sought to understand the barriers faced by local actors, validate whether the services addressed these barriers, and identify refinements needed to ensure a stronger fit with regional contexts.

A human-centred methodology guided the process. This began with a pilot-lead training session to harmonise approaches across regions. It was followed by in-person workshops to introduce the services, continuous support through the Enrich in Africa (EiA) platform, and structured feedback sessions to gather insights directly from innovators, hubs, and researchers. This sequence of activities created an evidence-based feedback loop that enabled learning, adaptation, and iteration throughout the pilot phase.

The motivation behind this work is clear: digital tools and services intended to strengthen ecosystems must be validated by their intended users. By engaging stakeholders directly, the pilots revealed both the strengths and the limitations of the SEADE services. The insights gained provide a foundation for refining the platform and associated activities, ensuring that they are inclusive, practical, and capable of driving meaningful collaboration and impact across Africa and Europe.

2. Deviations From The Work Plan

No deviation from the work plan.

3. Work Implemented and Results

3.1 Briefing of Pilot Leads

The piloting process began with the preparation of regional coordinators through a dedicated Pilot-Lead Training Workshop. Conducted online in Month 6, this workshop brought together 25 participants representing the lead organisations in Ghana (HAPA and the AAU), Kenya (WAZI and AAU), Senegal (BOND and BPI), and South Africa (MET, TIA and EiAC).

The training, facilitated with methodological input from S2i, introduced a human-centred approach to data collection and analysis, emphasising that the services needed to reflect the lived experiences of innovators and research actors. Participants were trained to design and use qualitative and quantitative research instruments, enabling them to capture not only perceptions but also evidence of usability and service relevance.

By the end of the session, pilot leads reported increased confidence in guiding local actors and collecting actionable insights. The workshop produced a harmonised piloting framework and shared instruments that ensured comparability of results across the four regions, while still allowing for local adaptation.

3.1.1 Ghana – Workshops and Feedback

Ghana's piloting activities were coordinated by HAPA and AAU. The process included a series of workshops designed to engage innovation hubs, startups, universities, and research organisations.

First EiA Workshop with Innovation Hubs and Startups (November 2024)

The first **in-person workshop in Accra (Nov 2024)** convened **22 participants**, including innovation hubs, accelerators, startups, and innovators. The session introduced participants to the **ENRICH in Africa Center (EiAC) platform**, with live demonstrations on how to register as Champions, post offerings, and access opportunities through the Marketplace, Twinning Programme, and capacity-building services.

Engagement outcomes:

- **Hubs & Accelerators:**
 - One hub showed the highest engagement, leveraging EiA programmes such as the Mentorday Acceleration Program and exploring the Champion Programme.
 - Two of the hubs registered but recorded **low** engagement due to confusion about navigation and setup.

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- One of the hubs was uncertain about completing registration and required follow-up.
- Two hubs provided no feedback and will need re-engagement.
- Overall, 1 of 6 hubs (**≈17%**) maintained consistent post-registration engagement.
- **Startups:**
 - Five startups registered but did not continue engagement after the event.
 - One startup experienced technical difficulties with the registration page.
 - This revealed a clear onboarding and retention gap, as most startups disengaged shortly after sign-up.
- **Researchers & Innovators:**
 - One researcher registered and applied as a mentor/trainer, looking forward to being engaged.

Part II – Workshop for Universities and Research Organisations (March 27, 2025)

Recognising the strategic role of academia in driving innovation, the AAU and HAPA co-organised a session titled “Unlocking New Opportunities with ENRICH in Africa (EiA): Empowering Universities & Researchers in Ghana” at the AAU Secretariat in Accra. The workshop brought together 16 participants from Ghanaian universities and research institutions.

Participants explored the EiAC platform’s advanced tools, including the Marketplace for Innovation and Capacity-Building Programmes, learning how to use them for academic collaboration, technology transfer, and funding access. The session emphasised helping researchers move their outputs from lab to market through EiA digital services.

Results:

- **14 participants (75%) registered as EiA Champions**, gaining access to funding, partnerships, and innovation resources.
- Feedback was overwhelmingly positive, highlighting the platform’s potential to connect research with practical applications.
- Universities expressed interest in using EiA tools for proposal development, collaborative research, and partnerships with European institutions.

Feedback Session (August 2025)

A dedicated feedback session held in August 2025 engaged 20 participants, including earlier attendees. Structured discussions and a Mentimeter survey produced the following findings:

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- 80% of respondents found the platform useful for discovering opportunities.
- 60% identified funding and matchmaking as the most relevant features.
- 30–40% requested additional onboarding support, such as explainer videos and simplified navigation.
- Participants also highlighted the need for greater visibility of local hubs in the Digital Innovation Hub (DIH) directory and more consistent follow-up communication after registration.

Overall Insight

The Ghana pilot provided a layered understanding of platform adoption across multiple user segments. Early engagement from hubs and startups revealed challenges with onboarding and sustained use, while the university and research community demonstrated high conversion rates and immediate uptake—with 14 Champions created in a single session. Together, these results show that EiA services can serve the full Ghanaian innovation ecosystem when supported by targeted training, localisation, and consistent follow-up.

3.1.2 Senegal – Workshops and Feedback

Senegal’s piloting activities, coordinated by BOND, consisted of three main sessions—two introductory workshops and a feedback workshop. The aim was to introduce local innovators to the EiA ecosystem, assess initial awareness, and gather structured feedback on usability and relevance.

First Workshop (14 November 2024 – Dakar)

The session brought together 12 participants from startups, hubs, and research organisations. Conducted in French, the workshop focused on raising awareness of EiA platform regarding its content and features (EuroQuity, Innowwide, AfriConEU Toolkit, Euraxess, and BIC Africa) and the following one talking about the EiA tools.

Quantitative results (Mentimeter):

- **EuroQuity:** 4 participants (~33%) familiar
- **BIC Africa:** 1 participant (~8%) familiar
- **Innowwide, AfriConEU Toolkit, Euraxess:** 0 familiar
- **No prior familiarity:** 8 participants (~67%), indicating that most attendees were new to EiA tools.

Familiarity with wider innovation initiatives:

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- **Africa: The Big Deal:** 10 participants ($\approx 83\%$) *did not know it*.
- **Digital Africa:** 7 ($\approx 58\%$) unfamiliar; 3 ($\approx 25\%$) aware and positive.
- **Digital Collective Africa:** 11 ($\approx 92\%$) unfamiliar.
- **AfricArena Wired:** 10 ($\approx 83\%$) unfamiliar.

Recommendations for other tools:

Participants suggested complementary platforms such as WEKOMKOM, PERSISTENT, LAUNCH AFRICA reflecting a strong interest in connecting EiA with local African initiatives.

Takeaway:

The first workshop revealed a low awareness of both the platform and its services but strong enthusiasm to explore them. Participants appreciated the exposure to cross-continental tools and urged for French translations, localized opportunities, and continued sensitization workshops to build familiarity.

Feedback Workshop (17 July 2025 – Dakar)

A follow-up session with **9 participants** assessed registration progress and service usability.

Adoption and registration:

- **3 participants** had completed registration.
- **2 were pending**, mainly due to time or process difficulties.
- Most confirmed that this follow-up encouraged them to register.

Perceived value:

- 45% of respondents rated the new services as “interesting” or “very interesting.”
- 33% said the services met their needs, particularly in discovering funding and partnership opportunities.
- Participants valued EiA’s potential for connecting Senegalese innovators with European networks.

Challenges and improvement needs:

- Language barriers remained the top concern.
- The registration process was described as too long.
- Participants found many calls and opportunities EU-centric and requested more Africa-focused content.
- Suggested enhancements included better filtering by country/sector and simplified onboarding.

Key insight:

The Senegal pilot demonstrated high enthusiasm and curiosity about EIA tools but highlighted critical barriers to adoption, including language, registration complexity, and lack of contextualized content. Both workshops collectively underscored the need for translation, regional customization, and ongoing capacity-building for sustained engagement across Francophone Africa.

3.1.3 Kenya – Workshops and Feedback

Kenya’s piloting activities, led by **WAZI** and the **AAU**, included two main events — an introductory **in-person workshop at EldoHub (November 25, 2024)** and a **virtual feedback workshop (August 22, 2025)**.

First Workshop (November 25, 2024 – Eldoret)

The first session engaged 10 IoT innovators selected from 31 applicants across Kenya’s North Rift region. Facilitated by WAZI with support from the AAU, the workshop introduced three key EIA services — Marketplace for Innovation, Twinning Programme, and Capacity Building via EIA Champions.

Participants identified major barriers to innovation including limited access to technical tools, weak mentorship structures, financing challenges, and commercialisation hurdles. During group discussions, they matched these local challenges with relevant EIA and legacy tools such as WaziLab, EuroQuity, Innowwide, and AfriConEU Toolkit, acknowledging their potential to:

- Address skills and mentorship gaps through AfriConEU and WaziLab;
- Improve access to finance via EuroQuity and BIC Africa;
- Enable global collaboration through the Twinning and Euraxess networks.

The workshop concluded with a call for EldoHub to act as a local focal point for EIA platform access and to establish a subscription-based IoT community linking innovators to EIA tools.

Feedback Workshop (22 August 2025)

The feedback session brought together **9 participants** from the original cohort, facilitated by **WAZI and AAU**. The discussion focused on post-training adoption of EIA services and user experience with platform tools.

Findings from the Google Form responses:

- **Awareness and usage:** 80% of participants reported that they had either registered or explored the EiA platform following the first workshop.
- **Adoption intent:** 100% expressed strong willingness to use the EiA tools regularly.
- **Usefulness:** 70% rated the EiA Marketplace and Capacity Building modules as “*very relevant*” to their business growth.
- **Ease of use:** 65% described the platform as intuitive but requested tutorials and visual onboarding support.
- **Top requested services:** Twinning Programme, Marketplace for Innovation, and Funding Discovery Tools.
- **Challenges cited:** Internet connectivity limitations, unfamiliarity with advanced features, and absence of localised examples of successful projects.

Participants recommended developing case studies from African startups, including those in Kenya, to contextualise EiA resources and improve relatability for grassroots innovators.

Key insight:

The Kenya pilot highlighted a strong link between digital readiness and local innovation adoption. The in-person workshop successfully built enthusiasm, while the feedback session confirmed high retention and conversion rates (over 80% ongoing engagement). However, it also underlined the need for localized training materials, improved connectivity support, and practical examples to drive continuous engagement with the EiA platform.

3.1.4 South Africa – Workshops and Feedback

South Africa’s piloting activities were co-led by MET and the EiAC. Two key sessions were held: an introductory Research & Innovation (R&I) Actor Workshop in Johannesburg on 26 March 2025, and a follow-up Pilot Region Stakeholder Feedback Session on 30 July 2025.

First Workshop (26 March 2025 – Johannesburg)

The R&I Actor Workshop was hosted in partnership with the AfricArena Johannesburg Summit. It attracted approximately 25 participants, exceeding the initial target of 20. The session featured an intimate, discussion-based setup that encouraged meaningful exchanges among research institutions, innovation hubs, investors, and policymakers.

A highlight of the event was the participation of a delegation from the Association of Startup and SME Enablers of Kenya (ASSEK), which fostered cross-border discussions on ecosystem development and collaborative opportunities between Kenyan and South African innovation stakeholders.

Key discussion themes:

- Funding mechanisms and Europe–Africa partnerships were identified as high-priority areas for strengthening R&I ecosystems.
- Participants requested deeper case studies demonstrating successful R&I funding models.
- Several attendees highlighted the lack of structured feedback channels for research institutions to communicate with funding agencies.
- Stakeholders agreed that SEADE’s ecosystem mapping and digital platform could play a critical role in addressing these gaps by improving coordination, visibility, and collaboration.

Engagement outcomes:

- The workshop successfully established new linkages between regional ecosystem actors.
- 5 participants expressed interest in continued collaboration, including participation in future SEADE and EiA activities.
- Participants commended the session for its relevance and interactivity but recommended more practical case examples and ongoing engagement through the SEADE Digital Environment on the EiA platform.

Feedback Workshop (30 July 2025)

The second session, led by MET, TIA, and EiAC, focused on collecting structured feedback from stakeholders who had engaged with the platform since the March event. The online workshop recorded 34 participants, including 10 returnees from previous sessions, signalling high retention.

Findings from the feedback surveys:

- **100% of participants** indicated intent to use the SEADE tools regularly.
- **80% found the EiAC platform intuitive** and easy to navigate.
- **Innowide** ranked as the most useful tool, followed by **Digital Collective Africa** and **AfricArena**.
- Sentiments such as “*engaging*,” “*insightful*,” and “*forward-thinking*” were frequently cited in participant responses.
- **Areas for improvement:**
 - **STR Actor Dashboard usability** scored low (average 1.2–3.6).

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- Moderate ecosystem alignment (average 1.8–2.4) signalled the need for **better contextual integration**.
- Participants requested **repository updates, tutorials, and AI-driven matchmaking features** to enhance experience.

Key insight:

The South Africa pilot demonstrated a progressive engagement trajectory—starting from strategic stakeholder dialogue in March to concrete usability feedback in July. High adoption intent and platform relevance were balanced by a call for improved user experience and stronger localisation. Collectively, these sessions underscored the importance of continuous engagement, content enrichment, and regional integration to sustain momentum.

Comparative Summary – Task 5.3 Pilots

Country	Participants (Workshops)	Adoption Intent	Top Services / Tools of Interest	Key Challenges Identified
Ghana	22 (Nov 2024 – hubs/startups) + 16 (Mar 2025 – universities) + 20 (Aug 2025 – feedback)	75% of researchers became EiA Champions; 70%+ of hubs/startups registered; 80% found the platform useful	EiA Marketplace (funding & matchmaking); Capacity Building for researchers	Low post-event engagement among hubs/startups; onboarding & retention gaps; need for stronger follow-up and DIH visibility
Senegal	12 (Nov 2024 – introduction) + 9 (July 2025 – feedback)	3 participants registered; strong intent among others to complete registration	EuroQuity (33% familiarity), BIC Africa (8%), Digital Africa, funding and partnership tools	Language barrier (French); long registration; EU-centric calls; 67% of first participants were new to EiA tools

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Kenya	10 (Nov 2024 – introduction) + 9 (Aug 2025 – feedback)	80% registered or explored EiA; 100% plan to continue using tools	EiA Marketplace, Twinning Programme, Capacity Building, WaziLab, EuroQuity	Internet connectivity challenges; need for localised content; limited advanced feature knowledge; mentorship gaps
South Africa	25 (Mar 2025 – Johannesburg) + 34 (July 2025 – feedback, 10 returnees)	100% plan to use SEADE tools regularly; strong cross-border engagement with ASSEK (Kenya)	Innowwide, Digital Collective Africa, AfricArena; EiAC platform and STR Dashboard	Low dashboard usability (1.2–3.6 avg.); moderate ecosystem alignment (1.8–2.4 avg.); need for repository updates, AI features, and case studies

3.2 Snapshots of STR Actor Feedback

3.2.1 Ghana Feedback Workshop

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How intuitive did you find the EiAC platform navigation?

21

Which AU-EU tools are most relevant to your work?

22

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Rate the usefulness of the STR Actor dashboard

21

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How likely are you to use these tools regularly?

19

3.2.2 Senegal Feedback Workshop

Avec le(s)quel(s) de ce(s) outil(s) êtes-vous familier ?

Notez : Africa: The Big Deal

Notez : Digital Africa

Notez : Digital Collective Africa

Notez : AfricArena Wired

3.2.3 Kenya Feedback Session

How easy was it to navigate the SEADE Digital Environment?

8 responses

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How easy was it to find the different features of the SEADE Digital Environment?

8 responses

Which service was most interesting to you? - Checkbox (Bootcamp, Twinning, Softlanding, Mentoring, Webinars, Startup Fund Opportunity, Lear...pedition, Capacity Building, Innovative Challenge)

8 responses

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For the service selected, what was interesting about that service?

8 responses

Which AU-EU tool was most interesting to you?

8 responses

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Which other AU-EU tool do you know that would be interesting for the platform?

8 responses

3.2.4 South Africa Feedback Workshop

How intuitive did you find the EiAC platform navigation?

Which AU-EU tools are most relevant to your work?

Rate the usefulness of the STR Actor dashboard

How likely are you to use these tools regularly

Key Survey Insights from the Feedback

- 100% Will Use Tools**
- 80% Platform Usability** - Found navigation intuitive (4 "somewhat", 1 "very") - strong foundation for adoption
- Innowwide Most Relevant**
- 2.4 Dashboard Rating** - STR Actor dashboard scored 1.2-3.6 average - needs usability improvements
- 2.2 SA Ecosystem Fit** - Moderate alignment (1.8-2.4) suggests need for local context adaptation
- 10 Return Attendees** - Strong ongoing engagement from previous workshop participants

4. Conclusion

The piloting of SEADE services across Ghana, Senegal, Kenya, and South Africa has provided compelling evidence of both the relevance and the potential of the ENRICH in Africa (EiA) platform. Through a cycle of training, workshops, ongoing support, and feedback sessions, the project reached innovators, hubs, and research actors in diverse contexts and generated insights that go beyond simple adoption metrics.

Across all four regions, participants expressed a clear willingness to engage with the platform and integrate its services into their daily activities. Adoption intent was consistently high, with 70–100% of participants indicating plans to use the tools regularly. The EiA Marketplace, funding and partnership services, and specialised instruments such as EuroQuity, Innowide, and WaziLab were seen as especially valuable.

At the same time, the pilots highlighted specific barriers that must be addressed to maximise impact. Ghanaian innovators emphasised the importance of onboarding support and stronger representation of local hubs. Senegalese stakeholders stressed the need for French translation, simplified registration, and more balanced opportunities. Kenyan startups underlined gaps in technical expertise, prototyping resources, and regulatory frameworks. South African participants confirmed strong engagement but called for improvements to the STR Actor Dashboard, enriched repositories, and closer alignment with the national ecosystem.

Together, these findings illustrate that while the SEADE services are highly relevant, their effectiveness will depend on continuous adaptation to local needs and user experiences. The pilots have thus created a robust evidence base that will inform platform refinement and service design in the next phases of the project.

5. Recommendations

Based on the pilots, several key recommendations emerge:

1. **Strengthen onboarding support:** Develop explainer videos, step-by-step guides, and tutorials to make entry into the platform easier for new users.
2. **Enhance inclusivity:** Translate content into French and potentially other languages to ensure wider accessibility across Africa. Audit the platform for accessibility to potential users with sensory disabilities (as suggested by the SEADE Ethics Advisor).

3. **Localise services:** Tailor opportunities, resources, and content to reflect the realities of different regional ecosystems, rather than relying heavily on EU-centric calls.
4. **Improve platform usability:** Prioritise upgrades to the STR Actor Dashboard, streamline tools to avoid duplication, and ensure regular repository updates.
5. **Support ecosystem anchoring:** Work with local hubs and focal points (such as EldoHub in Kenya and Bond'innov in Senegal) to sustain engagement and provide hands-on guidance to innovators.

Implementing these recommendations will not only address the gaps identified but also build on the strong momentum of adoption already observed. This will ensure that SEADE services evolve into an inclusive, practical, and widely used resource that strengthens Europe–Africa collaboration and accelerates the pathway from research to market.

